

LAMINATE HYBRIDIZATION USING HIGH MODULUS CARBON THIN PLYS FOR ENHANCED COMPRESSIVE PERFORMANCE

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The Composites Centre
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PRESENTATION OUTLINE

- Introduction
- Test methodology and hybrid laminate configurations.
- Experimental results of M55J in a carbon/carbon hybrid laminate.
- Fragmentation images of M55J fibres in an interrupted test.
- Experimental results of M55J in a glass/carbon hybrid laminate.
- Is the hybrid laminate failure affected as the thickness of M55J increases?
- Conclusion

NEXTCOMP

Aim: Develop a new generation of hierarchical composite materials to improve the compressive performance of fibre-reinforced composites.

Challenge: The longitudinal compressive strength of fibre-reinforced composites can be as low as half of their longitudinal tensile strength.

A collaboration between the University of Bristol and Imperial College London to address the challenges of longitudinal compression of composites.

Hierarchical problem

Modified from sources including; ST Pinho et al., On longitudinal compressive failure of carbon-fibre-reinforced polymer: from unidirectional to woven, and from virgin to recycled, *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A*, Vol. 370, Issue 1965, 2012, 1871-1895; R Gutkin et al., On the transition from shear-driven fibre compressive failure to fibre kinking in notched CFRP laminates under longitudinal compression, *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 70, Issue 8, 2010, 1223-1231.

BACKGROUND

Tensile stress–strain response of conventional and thin-ply interlayer hybrid composites and typical appearance of thin-ply hybrid specimens at successive damage phases (dark areas show bonded, light areas show damaged glass/carbon interface through the translucent outer glass layer) [1].

Compressive behaviour of $[\pm 27_7/0]_S$ MR60/M55J carbon layup, a) Pseudo-ductile stress-strain response and b) compressive ply fragmentation in the central 0° plies [2].

HYBRID LAMINATES

Material	Ply thickness (mm)	E_{11} (GPa)	Compressive Strain
IM7/epoxy	0.125	150	1.36% [3]
M55J/epoxy	0.030	240	0.31% [4]

- Observe if fragmentation of M55J occurs in a carbon/carbon hybrid laminate.
- Is the laminate failure affected as M55J thickness increases?

Cross-section view of the sandwich structure

TEST SET UP

- Instron 8872 Universal testing machine.
- Four-point bend test fixture.
- High speed camera recording at 50,000 fps.
- System 8000 data logger.
- AE sensors to detect fragmentation audially.

Note:

Support span of 550 mm.

Loading nose span of 60 mm (gauge section).

2 strain gauges attached on top and bottom skin.

2 AE sensors positioned in gauge section.

SINGLE PLY OF M55J

IM7
M55J
IM7
IM7
M55J
IM7

The maximum compressive strain of the hybrid laminate is 0.41% to 0.71%.

Intraply (**fragmentation**) failure of M55J followed by **delamination failure** of M55J and IM7 leading to catastrophic failure.

PSEUDO-DUCTILE RESPONSE OF SINGLE PLY OF M55J IN CARBON/CARBON HYBRID LAMINATES

High speed recording of sample 5 failure at 0.72% compressive strain.

Observe this area

DOUBLE PLY OF M55J

The maximum compressive strain of the hybrid laminate is 0.44% to 0.51%.

Intraply (**fragmentation**) failure of M55J followed by **instant delamination** failure of M55J and IM7 leading to catastrophic failure.

IM7
M55J
M55J
IM7
IM7
M55J
M55J
IM7

Longitudinal compression of [IM7/M55J₂/IM7]₂ laminate

Longitudinal compression of [IM7/M55J₂/IM7]₂ laminate

TRIPLE PLY OF M55J

The maximum compressive strain of the hybrid laminate is 0.36% to 0.47%.

Sample 5 was interrupted at 0.43% compressive strain after a load drop at 0.42% compressive strain.

IM7
M55J
M55J
M55J
IM7
IM7
M55J
M55J
M55J
IM7

High speed recording of sample 4 failure at 0.47% compressive strain.

Longitudinal compression of [IM7/M55J₃/IM7]₂ laminate

Longitudinal compression of [IM7/M55J₃/IM7]₂ laminate

TRIPLE PLY OF M55J

The sample was cut and polished to observe the fibre fragmentation of M55J.

Sample 5

Sample 5 cross-section

Sample 5 hybrid laminate cross-section

TRIPLE PLY OF M55J

Sample 5 hybrid laminate cross-section

IM7/913	t = 0.125 mm
M55J/TP402	t = 0.03 mm
M55J/TP402	t = 0.03 mm
M55J/TP402	t = 0.03 mm
IM7/913	t = 0.125 mm
IM7/913	t = 0.125 mm
M55J/TP402	t = 0.03 mm
M55J/TP402	t = 0.03 mm
M55J/TP402	t = 0.03 mm
IM7/913	t = 0.125 mm

TRIPLE PLY OF M55J

Fragmentation is observed on a fibre level and ply level

1. Compressive failure of M55J plies showing stable initial fragmentation.

TRIPLE PLY OF M55J

IM7
M55J
M55J
M55J
IM7
IM7
M55J
M55J
M55J
IM7

M55J baseline compressive strain of 0.31% and a knee point strain of 0.49% [4, 5].

Hybridization can support delayed compressive fragmentation of M55J.

Longitudinal compression of [IM7/M55J₃/IM7]₂ laminate

Longitudinal compression of [IM7/M55J₃/IM7]₂ laminate

- | M55J Knee point strain
- | M55J Baseline compressive strain

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS OF M55J IN GLASS/CARBON HYBRID LAMINATES

HYBRID LAMINATES

Material	Ply thickness (mm)	E_{11} (GPa)	Compressive Strain
S-glass/epoxy	0.125	45.7	2.33% [5]
M55J/epoxy	0.030	240	0.31% [4]

- Visually/audibly observe the fragmentation of M55J in a glass/carbon hybrid laminate.
- Is the laminate failure affected as M55J thickness increases?

Configuration 1 $E_{11} = 67.3 \text{ GPa}$ $t = 0.56 \text{ mm}$	Configuration 2 $E_{11} = 84.6 \text{ GPa}$ $t = 0.62 \text{ mm}$	Configuration 3 $E_{11} = 98.7 \text{ GPa}$ $t = 0.68 \text{ mm}$
S-glass	S-glass	S-glass
M55J	M55J	M55J
S-glass	M55J	M55J
S-glass	S-glass	M55J
M55J	S-glass	S-glass
S-glass	M55J	S-glass
	M55J	M55J
	M55J	M55J
	S-glass	S-glass

SINGLE PLY OF M55J

S-glass
M55J
S-glass
S-glass
M55J
S-glass

The maximum compressive strain of the hybrid laminate is 1.22% to 1.5%.

Pseudo-ductile compressive failure showing a knee point indicating **fragmentation** of M55J fibres occurs as **load is transferred to the surrounding S-glass fibres** followed by catastrophic failure.

Sample 6 at a failure compressive strain of 1.29%.

SINGLE PLY OF M55J REPEATED TEST

[S-glass/M55J₁/S-glass]₂ Laminate (Sample 5 repeated tests)

- 0.3% compressive strain
- 0.5% compressive strain
- 0.8% compressive strain
- 1.2% compressive strain
- Linear (1.1% compressive strain)
- 0.35% compressive strain
- 0.55% compressive strain
- 0.9% compressive strain
- 1.3% compressive strain
- Linear (1.5% compressive strain)
- 0.4% compressive strain
- 0.6% compressive strain
- 1% compressive strain
- 1.4% compressive strain
- 0.45% compressive strain
- 0.7% compressive strain
- 1.1% compressive strain
- 1.5% compressive strain

DOUBLE PLY OF M55J

The maximum compressive strain of the hybrid laminate is 0.7% to 0.92%.

Intraply (fragmentation) failure of M55J showing visible fibre breaks followed by delamination failure of M55J and load transfer to the surrounding S-glass fibres followed by catastrophic failure.

Pseudo-ductile compressive failure showing a knee point at 0.49% compressive strain.

S-glass
M55J
M55J
S-glass
S-glass
M55J
M55J
S-glass

Sample 4 failed at 0.86% compressive strain with M55J fibre fragments visible on laminate top plane.

DOUBLE PLY OF M55J REPEATED TEST

[S-glass/M55J₂/S-glass]₂ Laminate (Sample 1 repeated tests)

- 0.3% compressive strain
- 0.4% compressive strain
- 0.47% compressive strain
- 0.55% compressive strain
- 0.6% compressive strain
- 0.7% compressive strain
- 0.8% compressive strain

Sample 3 @ 0.5% strain

Sample 3 @ 0.6% strain

TRIPLE PLY OF M55J

The maximum compressive strain of the hybrid laminate is 0.39% to 0.46%.

Intraply (fragmentation) failure of M55J leading to **instant delamination and catastrophic failure**.

S-glass
M55J
M55J
M55J
S-glass
S-glass
M55J
M55J
M55J
S-glass

Sample 4 failed at 0.46% compressive strain.

TRIPLE PLY OF M55J REPEATED TEST

Sample 1 failed at 0.40% compressive strain.

MAXIMUM COMPRESSIVE STRAIN OF HYBRID LAMINATES

Average	CV (%)
4130	8.54
4320	6.27
4888	3.87
8360	9.49
5558	21.90
13667	7.21

--- Baseline strain [4]

--- Knee point strain [5]

CONCLUSION

High modulus fibres can be used to **increase the initial stiffness** of fibre reinforced composite laminates.

Hybridization of M55J fibres **demonstrates an increase in the compressive performance**.

The failure mechanism shows **compressive fragmentation of M55J fibres** that eventually **lead to delamination** followed by **catastrophic failure of the hybrid laminate**.

The **compressive strain of M55J** shows a **knee point at 0.49%** against the literature's baseline value of 0.31% indicating an increase in the compressive performance.

Increasing M55J thickness reduces the maximum compressive strains of the hybrid laminate.

Carbon/carbon hybrid laminates show **higher failure stresses** and **lower failure strains** than glass/carbon hybrids.

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